

Questionnaire – A Countrywide Descriptive Survey of Agile Software Development in Brazil

Number	Reference	Question	Answer options
1	-	What is your gender?	Male Female Other
2	DIEL et al. (2015)	How old are you?	< 26 26-35 36-45 > 45
3	DIEL et al. (2015)	In which company do you work? This information is not mandatory.	<open question>
4	MELO et al. (2013)	What is the size of your company? (number of employees)	< 9 people 10-49 people 50-99 people 100-999 people >1000 people
5	MELO et al. (2013)	In which state of Brazil is your company located?	<list of Brazilian states>
6	RODRIGUEZ et al. (2012)	What is the size of your team?	1-5 6-10 11-20 21-50 > 50
7	KUHRMANN et al. (2017)	Is your team distributed?	No Yes, in the same country Yes, in the same continent Yes, globally
8	Version One (2017)	What is your company industry?	Education Government Manufacturing Media and entertainment Consumer products Healthcare Insurance Financial services Professional services Public services Internet services Software Telecommunications Transportation Utilities Retail Other <open question>

9	RODRIGUEZ et al. (2012)	How long have you been working with software development?	< 1 year 1-2 years 2-5 years 5-10 years 10-20 years > 20 years
10	DIEL et al. (2015)	What is your schooling level?	High school Undergraduate MBA and similar Masters Doctorate
11	Version One (2017)	What is your experience level with agile software development?	Few experience/No knowledge Moderately experienced Very experienced Extremely experienced
12	Version One (2017)	How long have your company been using agile methods?	< 1 year 1-2 years 3-5 years 6-10 years > 10 years
13	Version One (2017)	Which is the agile method used in your company? You may choose more than one.	Scrum Scrum/XP Hybrid Custom Hybrid (multiple methodologies) Scrumban Kanban Iterative Development Lean Development Lean Startup Feature-Driven Development DSDM/Atern XP Agile Unified Process (Agile UP) I do not know Other
14	KUHRMANN et al. (2017)	Does your company combine agile methods with traditional ones to develop software?	Yes No
15	Version One (2017)	How many teams in your company apply agile methods?	None of our teams is agile Less than half of our teams are agile More than half of our teams are agile All of our teams are agile

16	DIEL et al. (2015) - adapted	How frequent is the application of these principles in your company? (Frequently, Rarely, Never, and Do not know)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attention to technical excellence Building projects around motivated individuals Easily adapting to changes Getting to know product value based on customer perception Inspecting team members work Limiting Work in Progress (WIP) Measuring progress with working software Prioritizing face-to-face communication between stakeholders Reducing work that does not add value to the customer Responding to changes more than following a plan Solving problems with simple solutions Transparency in work and communication with team members Valuing continuous improvement Valuing customer collaboration over contract negotiation Valuing individuals and interactions over processes and tools Valuing self-organizing teams Valuing working software more than comprehensive documentation
17	Version One (2017)	Which are the reasons why your company adopted agile methods? You may choose more than one.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working together with business people Accelerate software delivery Better manage distributed teams Enhance the ability to manage changing priorities Enhance delivery predictability Enhance software quality Improve business/IT alignment Improve engineering discipline Improve project visibility Improve team morale Increase productivity Increase software maintainability Reduce project cost Reduce project risk Other

18	Version One (2017)	Which are the practices you have in your company?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agile portfolio planning Agile/lean UX Automated acceptance testing Behavior-driven Development Coding standards Collective code ownership Continuous deployment Continuous integration Daily standup Dedicated Product Owner Design Sprints Emergent design Frequent releases Kanban Open workspace Pair programming Product road mapping Refactoring Releases planning Retrospectives Short iterations Single team (integrated dev and test) Sprint/iteration planning Sprint/iteration review Sustainable pace Team estimation Test-driven development (TDD) User story mapping Other
19	Version One (2017)	Do you consider successful the agile projects in your company?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No Sometimes I do not know

20	DIEL et al. (2015)	Which challenges do you perceive in agile software development adoption? You may choose more than one.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities synchronization Agile methods scaling Agile practices customizing Cultural change Customer collaboration Decreasing predictability Defining business value Fixed-price contracts Inadequacy of existing technologies and tools Inadequate documentation Inadequate training Lack of formal guidance Loss of management control Measuring agile success Need for special skills Resistance to change Steep learning curve Top management commitment Translating agile principles from dev to business Troubles with self-management Other
21	DIEL et al. (2015)	How did the adoption of agile methods impact the following aspects? Classify as improved, no effect, got worse, or do not know.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ability to adapt to changes Ability to manage changing priorities Business/IT alignment Customer collaboration Customer comprehension Engineering discipline Learning and creating knowledge Managing distributed teams Productivity Project cost reduction Project predictability Project risks reduction Project visibility Self-management skills Software maintainability Software quality Stakeholders satisfaction Team collaboration Team communication Team morale Time to market Value creation Waste and excessive activities
